

Functional Assays for Solute Carrier Transporters

Thallium based assay for SLC12A2 using HEK-293 SLC12A2 OE cells

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Assay description

FLIPR® Potassium Assay Kit exploits the permeation of thallium ions (Tl^+) through both voltage-gated, ligand-gated potassium and potassium transporters. A highly sensitive Tl^+ indicator dye is used. This dye produces a bright fluorescent signal upon the binding to Tl^+ conducted through potassium channels and transporters. Therefore, it provides a functional indication of the potassium channel and transporter activities (Figure 1).

During the initial dye loading step, the dye is loaded into cells as a membrane-permeable acetoxymethyl (AM) ester. Once inside the cell, the AM ester form of the dye is cleaved by endogenous esterases into a fluorogenic thallium sensitive indicator.

The thallium sensitive form is retained in the cytosol and its extrusion is inhibited by Probenecid which blocks organic anion pumps.

The assay is usually carried out using Chloride free buffer (Tyrode's buffer 0 mM Cl^-): thallium forms an insoluble precipitate when chloride is present in the solution.

SLC12A2 (NKCC1) is an electroneutral cotransporter that mediates uptake of Na^+ , K^+ , and Cl^- in a ratio of 1:1:2 and is inhibited by 'loop diuretics' such as bumetanide.

It plays a role in neuronal Cl^- homeostasis secretion and represents a target for brain pathologies with altered NKCC1 function.

SLC12A2 has also been shown to participate in the maintenance and regulation of cell volume (transport of ions is also associated to water transport).

Being responsible for potassium transport, SLC12A2 is eligible to be studied using the Thallium assay.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR® Potassium Assay Kit. The assay exploits the permeation of thallium ions (Tl^+) through both voltage-gated, ligand-gated potassium and potassium transporters. A highly-sensitive Tl^+ indicator dye is used. This dye produces a bright fluorescent signal upon the binding to Tl^+ conducted through potassium channels and transporters. Therefore, it provides a functional indication of the potassium channel and transporter activities.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC12A2 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 15'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO_2 . At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 1 $\mu g/mL$ Doxycycline (not induced control in parallel).

Thallium assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 60 minutes at RT in 20 μL /well of Thallium Dye Loading Solution (AM dye 1X + probenecid 2.5 mM + masking solution prepared in Tyrode's Buffer Chloride free) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λ_{exc} 470 - 495nm / λ_{em} 515 - 575 nm filter.

To test pharmacology a double injection protocol was used. First injection: 5 μL /well (5X) of Tyrode's Buffer Chloride free (0.5% DMSO) or Bumetanide dose response, starting from 100 μM ,

semi-log dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included, prepared in Tyrode's Buffer Chloride free (0.5% DMSO)). Second injection: 25 μ L/w (2X) of Thallium D/R (from 15 mM, semi-log dilution) or Thallium 1/3 mM (~EC60/EC80 values) dissolved in Tyrode's buffer containing 25 mM Chloride (final concentration). Both injections performed online at plate reader and kinetic traces were recorded 5 minutes after first injection and 3 minutes after second injection. To assess robustness, reproducibility, and amenability to high-throughput screening in double injection protocol, five 384-well plates were run consecutively, using the following plate layout (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Plate layout for multiplate.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Background correction at pre-injection". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC) (60 seconds after second injection). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC50/IC50 values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC12A2
Synonyms	Bumetanide-Sensitive Sodium-(Potassium)-Chloride Cotransporter 2; NKCC1
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 12 (Sodium/Potassium/Chloride Transporters)
UniProt ID	P55011
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE035G-1 (HEK-SLC12A2-WTOE-p2)

Assay data

<p>Thallium D/R</p> <p>RFU (AUC, 1 min)</p> <p>log[Th⁺; M]</p> <p>EC₅₀ = 0.6 mM EC₈₀ = 3 mM</p> <p>● SLC12A2 induced ■ SLC12A2 not-induced</p>	Compound name (1)	Thallium
	PubChem CID	105005
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma, cat. #208191
	Mode of action	"Thallium Substrate" (it mimics Potassium)
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 0.6 mM
<p>Bumetanide D/R SLC12A2 (doxy-induced)</p> <p>RFU (AUC, 1 min)</p> <p>log[Bumetanide; M]</p> <p>● Thallium 1 mM ■ Thallium 3 mM</p>	Compound name (1)	Bumetanide
	PubChem CID	2471
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Thermo Fisher, cat. # J62302.03
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.8 μM
<p>rbZ'</p> <p>plate 1 plate 2 plate 3 plate 4 plate 5</p>	Z' factor calculated as	
		$RZ' = 1 - \frac{3 \cdot RSD(CR_p) + 3 \cdot RSD(SR_p)}{ \langle CR_p \rangle - \langle SR_p \rangle }$ <p>in double injection protocol</p>

	<p>Intraplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{CR} = \frac{SD(CR_p)}{ \overline{SR}_p - \overline{CR}_p } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{SR} = \frac{SD(SR_p)}{ \overline{SR}_p - \overline{CR}_p } \times 100$ <p>in double injection protocol</p>
	<p>Interplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Interplate}_{CR} = \frac{\overline{CR}_p - \text{mean}(\overline{CR}_{p,d})}{ \overline{CR}_{p,d} - \overline{SR}_{p,d} } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Interplate}_{SR} = \frac{\overline{SR}_p - \text{mean}(\overline{SR}_{p,d})}{ \overline{CR}_{p,d} - \overline{SR}_{p,d} } \times 100$ <p>in double injection protocol</p>

Discussion

The Thallium based assay for SLC12A2 showed a strong, specific and dose-dependent fluorescent signal decrease in target cells upon Bumetanide injection. IC₅₀ values are stable and reproducible. DMSO up to 1.5% does not affect pharmacology nor assay window.

The assay fulfils the HTS quality criteria.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).